

D. 7.2 – Initial data management plan including Protection of Personal Data (POPD)

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Delivery date	31/07/2023
Dissemination level	Public

gEneSys

Initial data management plan

<i>Project Acronym</i>	GeneSys
<i>Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Project Full Title</i>	gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe

Deliverable Information

<i>Deliverable Name</i>	Initial data management plan including Protection of Personal Data (POPD)
<i>Dissemination level</i>	D. 7.2
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe
<i>Grant Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Contractual date of delivery</i>	30/07/2023
<i>Deliverable Leader</i>	IRPPS-CNR
<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	Lucio Pisacane
<i>Keywords</i>	Initial data management plan, Protection of Personal Data
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This report deals with gEneSys Data Management Plan, the data management cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated during the life of the project. This will include information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the handling of research data during and after the end of the project. • what data will be collected, processed and/or generated. • which methodology and standards will be applied. • whether data will be shared/made open access. • how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

Document history

<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
31/07/2023	V.01	IRPPS-CNR	First Draft	n/a
XXX	V.01	IAO-Cerri	Second draft	n/a

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1 INTRODUCTION

As defined in art. 15 of the Grant Agreement and following the principles described in the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020¹ gEneSys project will ensure open access to all scientific publications and to research data: each beneficiary will disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, such as scientific publications (ad hoc guidelines containing publication policies in gEneSys will be produced), in order to maximise opportunities for future researchers, foster collaborations, finalise efforts and so on. This does not change the obligation to protect results, the confidentiality and security in Article 13, or the obligations to protect personal data, all of which still apply.

Having the overall objective to implement research aimed at studying the nexus between gender and energy transition/transformation to transform gender interrelations of power in the energy sector, the gEneSys project will draw on both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (specifically in WP1, WP2 and WP3).

After successfully completing the initial phase of the project, which involved conducting a systematic literature review on the relationship between gender and energy transition/transformation, developing an ontology of the energy system, and conducting a gendered assessment of the energy systems knowledge community and EU policies for sustainable energy systems, the project will now proceed to the next phase. In this phase, gEneSys will undertake various activities that require the collection of personal data. These activities will be further described in the following subsections:

- a multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems (WP1);
- a large N (30.000) cross-country survey (WP2);
- 60 semi-structured interviews (WP2);
- a Delphi study engaging experts improving their theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns (WP2);
- participatory observation of the teams working in the energy sector (WP3);
- Reflexive workshop with female energy researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs and leaders (WP3).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf

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In doing this, data management issues are raised and these will be considered as an ongoing and reflexive part of the research process throughout the life of the project.

1.1 Purpose and structure of the document

The purpose of this document is to introduce the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the gEneSys project. The DMP is a formal document that outlines how data is to be handled both during a research project, and after the project is completed.

Research data management poses a complex challenge due to the diverse nature of data, the variability of formats, and the challenges of accessibility. Therefore, Horizon Europe mandates the compilation of a DMP for each dataset, outlining the steps taken to ensure the long-term usability of the data. A DMP typically undergoes continuous development throughout the project's lifespan, documenting changes in the lifecycle of all datasets. The present document contains information about:

- Regulations and indications about Data Management in Horizon Europe.
- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated and how.
- Whether data will be shared/made open access and how data will be curated and preserved.

gEneSys will deliver updated DPM versions whenever important changes in the data policy occur and will disseminate an updated DPM document at month 18 when most of the data collection activities will be undergoing (D 7.9).

2. RULES AND REGULATIONS

2.1 Horizon Europe regulations

Horizon Europe beneficiaries are asked to make their research data FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed:

- Findable: the created datasets have to be described by sufficiently rich metadata and registered or indexed in a searchable resource. Digital assets should be uniquely identified through the use of Persistent Identifiers that are globally resolvable (PIDs).
- Accessible: data sets have to be obtainable by humans and machines upon appropriate authorisation and through a well-defined and universally implementable protocol.
- Interoperable: data sets are created in a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable format and when a language for knowledge representation is used.

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- Re-usable: rich metadata and documentation must be provided that follow relevant community standards and provide information on provenance.

The European Commission is running a flexible pilot under Horizon 2020 called the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD pilot). The ORD pilot aimed to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. It takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. From the 2017 work programme, the Open Research Data pilot has been extended now to cover all the thematic areas of Horizon 2020 and now in Horizon Europe.

This general principle has become even more important after the pandemic period. Making all research publications and research findings immediately available; making research data openly accessible; providing open access to all data that may be useful to researchers have become key factors in a time when transfers among places are harder and in person access to information is reduced.

2.2 Ethical aspects and data sharing

The main risks faced by gEneSys project are non-consented disclosure of the identity of interviewees and consulting experts and insufficient protection of sensitive private information associated with discrimination and stigmatisation, political orientations, and health condition of interviewees. Safeguarding privacy and appropriate measures for processing, handling, and storing data will be thus central at all stages of research and beyond.

The right to data protection is guaranteed by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. It gives effect to the right to privacy by providing individuals with autonomy and control over the way their information is collected and used. In research settings, data protection creates obligations on researchers to provide research subjects with detailed information about what will happen to the personal data that they collect from them and to comply to this information. Especially, it requires all data processing entities to ensure the data is properly protected, 'minimised', and destroyed when no longer needed.

As every EU-funded research project that processes personal data must, also gEneSys will comply with: EU and national data protection laws, ethical considerations and the values and principles underpinning the EU. Particular attention will be paid to the increasing impact of all forms of ICT on social and material life in the letter and spirit of the EU GDPR.

For a larger and comprehensive discussion on ethics in gEneSys project, please refer to the Deliverable 8.1 and, generally, to WP 8 on Ethics Requirements.

3. COLLECTION AND STORAGE OF DATA

3.1 Datasets in gEneSys

Data collection presents a big opportunity to pursue large-scale analyses in order to uncover valuable insights across many fields and disciplines. Potential follow-up studies on the basis of a data set are often hampered by inadequate and non-standardized documentation and preparation of data.

Sometimes, data are insufficiently described to understand what they are or how they were produced. A second issue is that data catalogues and data repositories use different metadata standards, and this prevents easy search and aggregation of data itself.

This is the reason why thorough data preparation and documentation in research projects are crucial. They are primarily divided into two types: primary (generated) data and secondary (already collected) data. gEneSys will collect and analyse both primary and secondary data, across WP1, WP2, and WP3. In particular, as stated in GA, tasks involved in the collection of data are:

1) T1.5. Data set: Stakeholder assessment [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 6-15)

The survey will contain detailed questions about women's participation and empowerment in energy transition, specifically collecting workers' opinions on the future of energy sector in terms of: i) professional needs of workers; ii), the relationship between women and the energy sector with regard to gender stereotypes and the skills of women workers; iii) strategies to attract young people to the study of STEM subjects, taking into account obstacles as well as potentials. The survey will involve stakeholder organisations operating in the sector of energy transition in four European countries participating in the project (i.e., Germany, Italy, Poland, UK) to identify differences and similarities.

2) T2.1. Intersectional citizen survey [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 7-21)

A service provider will be commissioned to collect a unique data set for the exploration of intersectional patterns within the gender-energy nexus for six EU member states and four sub-Saharan countries. A total of 30,000 citizens of the 10 target countries are surveyed about their experiences of marginalisation in connection with energy consumption and energy policy. The questions include income, self-assessment of health status, self-assessment as part of a discriminated group and a range of political orientations. Within the framework of this task, the data collection process will be coordinated with the survey provider, the field phase will be guided by gEneSys, including how the data are collected and processed for analysis.

3) T2.2 Data set: Delphi survey [PRIMARY DATA] (Months: 15-21)

The dataset collected in T2.1 will be exploratively analysed for intersectional patterns of marginalisation related to energy consumption and energy policy within the ten target countries. A Delphi survey will be organized with a group of 10-15 experts for the

co-creation process that will be identified by reputational sampling within the Advisory board and beyond. The expert panel members read the exploratory data report, and then answer a series of questions about it aimed at improving the theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns.

4) T2.3 Citizen interview transcripts (Months 14-26) [PRIMARY DATA]

Approximately 45-minute-long interviews will be conducted by the same service provider who conducted the data collection in T2.1 with 60 individuals using up to 10 interview guidelines provided by the research team. The service provider provide the research team with translated interview transcripts for analysis. The interview partners will be determined based on the data set collected, and in coordination with WP1 and WP3. The interview data are used to compile case studies with the aim to substantiate the intersectional data patterns and their theoretical explanations elaborated in the course of T2.1 and T2.2.

5) T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems (Months 8-24) [PRIMARY DATA]

T3.2 will use participatory and co-creation approaches involving university students and teachers to provide new insights and practical solutions to help universities revise their pedagogies and career advice by paying attention to the values of inclusion, sustainability, justice, and fairness when promoting skills and careers for the 'green new deal' panorama or jobs and careers.

6) T3.3 Increase the participation of women in energy systems and in advancing energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (Months 24-32) [PRIMARY DATA]

In order to design a long-term impact on the energy landscape, T3.3 will employ participatory and reflexive national workshops involving female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders. Building on the findings of T3.2 and T3.3, an international masterclass on pedagogy and training, focusing on gender aspects of energy transition, will be developed. Collaborating with WP4, T3.2 will create an information pack to assist the African Institute of Mathematical Sciences in attracting more women to their researcher training programs. At the next stage of the DMP (D7.9 Month 18), team leaders will provide detailed descriptions for the institutional data subsets collected or generated by the research teams.

3.2 gEneSys Data Managers

The National Research Council of Italy (CNR), leading partner, confirms that Dr. Lucio Pisacane, Scientific Coordinator of gEneSys project, and the management team have been appointed as Data Protection Officers (DPO) and that Management Office contact details will be made available to all data subjects involved in the research.

One of the main attention points will be to guarantee that all the data that will be processed during the life of the project will be relevant and limited to the purposes of the research, in accordance with the "data minimisation" principle (art. 5, GDPR), that says that data must be adequate (sufficient to properly fulfil your stated purpose),

relevant (has a rational link to that purpose), and limited to what is necessary (you do not hold more than you need for that purpose).

To obtain these outcomes, we will perform some necessary actions:

- promote adequate individual data collections that does not exceed the project purposes;
- avoid systematic collection or processing of sensitive data. If sensitive information is disclosed, it will in any event be treated anonymously and used exclusively when this is necessary for the analysis of cases relating to the research objectives;
- specific considerations will be done for specific sub-group of participants (i.e. see D 8.1 for further references) and
- ensure data availability only to authorised researchers who have provided sufficient institutional support and traceability of the use they make of the data.

3.3 Standards and metadata

Metadata will be created to describe the datasets produced for discoverability and identification.

The data collection from different partners will guarantee uniformity, comparability and reproducibility of the data. WP coordinators and team leaders will take any measure to ensure data accuracy and quality by following the common data collection grids (quantitative and qualitative checklists), training and supervising data collectors, monitoring and cross-checking data processing and analysis.

Folders should be named in a meaningful way so that they are easily discoverable, with systems that will allow to identify different versions and potentially different authors of different RPOs [i.e *WP number_Task number_type of data_Institution name_author's initials_DDMMYY*

Personal and sensitive data will be handled according to the gEneSys ethical policy (see § 2.2 here) and informed consent obtained from all participants. The data will also be converted from proprietary formats and made available in open well-known and documented formats to allow accessibility and reusability.

For security purposes and to preserve anonymity and confidentiality, individual personal data will be stored in a password protected file separated from the raw data. This password-protected file will be stored in the internal institutional repository.

At this stage it is not possible to provide an exact value for the data volume but we can provide an estimation that in any case could be subject to change when the data collection stage is completed. The volume of the data collection will be approximately 200 questionnaires for T1.5, 30.000 questionnaires for T2.1, 15 Delphi

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Surveys for T2.2, 60 transcripts of 45-minutes long interviews for T2.3, and XX [mc5] individuals involved in the co-creation activities for T3.2.

3.4 Technical aspects

Regarding the matter of anonymity, the adopted policy will prioritize utmost efforts to anonymize the collected data and minimize the risk of re-identification. However, it is important to note that data collection pertaining to specific sub-groups of participants, such as the gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems (WP1), may pose a potential risk of identification due to the public nature of their roles. For instance, the content of an interview could potentially reveal the identity of the interviewee due to the unique and specific nature of their role.

Permission to use personal data (including through publication) will be asked to subjects that have specific roles within the stakeholder organizations, since they might be willing to be mentioned (and thus identified). In case the consent is not given by the participant, the collected data will be duly anonymised (e.g., through aggregation) and, in case it is not possible, it will not be used in the analysis. A specific consent form will be prepared for the specific sub-group of participants if needed.

Data collected via recording (audio and video files) will be immediately downloaded from the recorder system on return to the researcher's office in a secure directory or secure file server. Information on the recorder is deleted directly afterwards. For the process of transcribing qualitative interviews, transcribers will follow strict confidentiality and data security protocols. Individual information on interviewees (such as names, nationalities, age, legal conditions) will be gathered but will be stored following principles of strictest confidentiality separately from the remaining collected information so that no information can be directly linked to the person of the respondent. Personal data collected will be used to create an alphanumeric code, that will guarantee anonymisation of participants and will be used during the research and later.

Data that can identify individuals will not be published or made available or passed on to third parties. The real name of each interviewee will be substituted by an alias. Same applies to other distinguishing personal information that will be replaced with a pseudonym. To any interviewee access to a copy of the anonymized personal interview will be granted upon request. The signed informed sheets are stored in a protected environment and separated from the remaining collected information so that no information can be directly linked to the person of the respondent.

All primary and secondary data collected by the gEneSys project will be securely stored on dedicated computers or file servers located at each data-collecting partner's premises. To ensure the security of the data, appropriate measures such as firewalls and password protection will be implemented on the computers and networks

Data access has to be restricted to authorised researchers of the project that will sign a data protection statement for the specific data set. Researchers will not be allowed to keep copies of the data sets beyond the agreed time window for data analyses or allow others to access the data sets. Analyses of the anonymized qualitative interviews

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and synopses will only be conducted according to research questions that will be defined during the project. It will not be allowed to publish full personal interviews. Researchers may only quote short passages of individual interviews in anonymized form. The collected personal data will be stored during the lifespan of the project. Within the end of the project they will be anonymised and the data will be used afterwards only in that form.

3.5 Template for creating datasets for each Institution

A) Dataset reference, name and description	
<p>1. Dataset name Provide a name or a title for the dataset. Es. WP2_Task2.3_quantitative-stakeholder_CNR_LP_150723</p>	
<p>2. Dataset ID If available, provide an identifier for your dataset. In addition, indicate the identifier type, such as for example: DOI, Handle, PURL, URL, URN.</p>	<p>Id: Id type:</p>
<p>3. Dataset origin, WP and current status 3.1 Collected datasets are dataset that use secondary data; generated datasets are based on data created within the project (primary data). 3.2 Indicate WP number and task number 3.3 Indicate dataset current status use one of the following: available; in progress; not available</p>	<p>3.1 Indicate if the dataset is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collected • Generated <p>3.2 WP:..... Task:.....</p> <p>3.3 Dataset current status (choose one option):</p>
<p>4. Dataset creators and contributors 4.1 Indicate the WP leaders and the team leaders involved in the dataset production and organization as dataset creators. Add other creators only if relevant. Fields for each role may be repeated if necessary. 4.2 The rights holder/s are persons or institutions owning or managing property rights including intellectual property rights over the dataset. Indicate the rights holders only if different from WP leaders and team leaders.</p>	<p>Fields for each role may be repeated if necessary.</p> <p>4.1 Dataset creator/s creator name: (family, given name) ORCID (http://orcid.org) (if available): Affiliation: Email: address:</p> <p>If different from creator/s, you may indicate other contributors involved in the dataset production and management. If not yet available, these fields may be filled at later stages.</p> <p>4.2 Rights Holder/s rights holder name: (family, given name) ORCID (http://orcid.org) (if available): Affiliation:</p>

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<p>4.3 The contact person is a person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise address issues related to the dataset. Indicate only if different from WP leaders and team leaders.</p> <p>4.4 Contributor type: Data Collector (such as survey conductors, interviewers...), Producer (person or organization responsible for the form of a media product), Project Member, Researcher (it may indicate an assistant to one of the authors who helped with research), Research Group, Other</p>	<p>4.3 Contact Person/s Contact person name: (family, given name) ORCID (http://orcid.org) (if available): Affiliation: Email: address:</p> <p>4.4 Dataset contributor/s Contributor type (choose an option from the guidance) Contributor name: (family, given name or name of organization) ORCID (http://orcid.org) (if available and applicable): Affiliation (if applicable):</p>
<p>5. Dataset Description Include the following issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nature of the data (for example: experimental observations; survey results; interview transcripts; simulation data; models; software; diaries; lab notebooks; ...); • the data scale (for example the number of the analyzed interviews ...) • the data sources (in case it is collected): provide full citation of the data sources; 	

B) Standards and metadata

<p>1. Methodologies for data collection or generation, data processing and quality assurance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe procedures for quality assurance that will be carried out on the data at the time of collection or generation, data entry, digitization and revision or validation. (E.g. quality control measures can include bias and/or scale of measurement; protocols for recording raw data; controlled vocabularies, code lists and choice lists; computer aided procedures to check data completeness; data cleaning procedures ...) 	
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<p>2. Describe typologies, content, format and quality of data Indicate whether the data are one or more of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● numerical, textual - graphical, visual or tactile ● created in digital form (born digital) or converted (digitized) ● quantitative o qualitative data ● raw, derived or secondary ● cleaned or processed <p>Data may be presented in a tabular, textual, graphical form, or may be audio or video.</p>	
<p>3. Metadata Indicate which metadata standard will be used to describe the dataset. Indicate which documentation will be provided along with data files. must be created to describe the dataset for discoverability and identification. Indicate which standards will be used to describe the dataset. (e.g. terms from a controlled vocabulary or thesaurus to indicate the subject of the dataset).</p>	

C) Data Sharing and dissemination

<p>1. Data accessibility and licensing 1.1 Actions for data sharing include anonymizing or aggregating data; gaining participant consent for data sharing; gaining copyright permissions; converting the file to standard open formats. Also explain how the shareable data are made available (e. g repository for dissemination, web site, reports, publications...)</p> <p>1.2 The level of accessibility may be related to all the dataset or its separated parts, or a specific version, if appropriate. Access must be given immediately at the time of publication for the data needed to validate the results. For all the other data, it will possible to specify an embargo period.</p>	<p>Describe dissemination procedures for the dataset.</p> <p>1.1 Procedures and the measures adopted to share the data:</p> <p>1.2 Choose the level of accessibility of the data of the dataset:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● open access ● immediately after dataset conclusion or at least at the time of publication of the research results as underlying data needed to validate publications; ● after an embargo period (indicate months and explain why) ● not available (explain why)
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<p>1.3 For example raw data may be kept confidential; while processed and analyzed data may be made widely open. Reasons for the impossibility to share data may be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the data belongs to third party and the consortium or the partner have not the permission for sharing it; ● the data are under confidentiality obligations; ● the data need to be kept confidential due to rules of personal data and ethical reasons; ● other (specify other reasons) <p>For example: Creative commons</p>	<p>1.3 Indicate, which versions or parts of the dataset cannot be shared and give the reasons (you can choose one of the options in the guidance)</p> <p>1.4 Indicate the license of data:</p>
<p>2. Repository for the dissemination of the dataset</p>	<p>Indicate the repository type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Institutional ● Disciplinary ● Other (specify) <p>Provide Name and URL for the repository:</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326